

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS

Murodov Oybek Turaqulovich

"ASIAN INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY"
Assistant teacher of "General technical sciences" department

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada umumta'lim maktablarining ta'lim jarayonida Hozirgi o'qitish jarayoniga qo'yiladigan talablarning asosiy prinsip va qoidalari imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar : Dars, tarbiya, taqdimot, multimedia, videolavha.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье выделены преимущества использования основных принципов и правил требований к действующему учебному процессу в образовательном процессе общеобразовательной школы.

Ключевые слова: Урок, тренинг, презентация, мультимедиа, видео

ABSTRACT

The article highlights the advantages of using the main principles and rules of requirements for the current teaching process in the educational process of general education schools.

Keywords: Lesson, training, presentation, multimedia, video

INTRODUCTION

In our independent Uzbekistan, the reform of the continuous education system, the reorganization of the education and training process based on new educational standards, special attention is paid to the activity of the teacher and his pedagogical skills.

Perfect organization of the lesson in continuous education is the primary task of the teacher. Lessons conducted at a high level remain in the minds of students for a long time, and have an effective impact on the formation of their faith, beliefs and ideologies. For this reason, the teacher's scientific level, attitude to his duty, enthusiasm for coaching young people, and pedagogical skills are known at the beginning of the lesson. The quality of the lesson also determines the grade of the science teacher.

MAIN PART

Currently, special attention is paid to the activity of the teacher and his pedagogical skills. Recommendations regarding the use of pedagogical technology in the course of the lesson, which have begun to take place in the pedagogical thinking of teachers working in the educational process, are very necessary for teachers. Interactive teaching methods aimed at sensing, feeling, controlling oneself, being able to express one's thoughts clearly, succinctly and carefully, using fast pictures are developing and giving positive results. The interactive methods used in teaching created an atmosphere of competition among students, encouraged them to be active, and as a result, students began to learn cooperation.

Any interactive method, when used correctly and purposefully, will teach students to think independently. New pedagogical technology is a process that produces rational ways of the

educational system, in which the teacher is the main responsible person. Because its main task is to deliver information to students quickly, accurately and clearly. , should be taught to draw conclusions. In this, the student is the main driving force, can read, read, draw, understand the formulas of projections and use tools, have friendly relations with each other, and help each other in solving the problems set before them.

their main task is to help.

In mastering the art of teaching, the lesson organized by the teacher, along with being a means of imparting deep knowledge, is the development of independent Uzbekistan, confidence in the future, what the intelligence and work of our people are capable of, a worthy citizen of the society and serves as a mirror of what it takes to become a teacher. The lesson places a great responsibility on the teacher. Currently, the concept of a modern lesson is often mentioned in pedagogy.

It can be seen from the above that the lesson is the main organizational form of education, and it is a didactic activity organized in a strict order with a certain number of regular students and directed towards a specific goal.

What needs to be done to enrich it with new elements that will increase students' interest in the lesson and the requirements of the current teaching process? The modern educational system requires not only mastering the knowledge that mankind has discovered, but also familiarization with the issues that society must solve and the students of today must participate in it. Such issues may include the exploitation of space, the peaceful use of atomic energy, the conversion of deserts into fertile lands and gardens, the intensification of agriculture, and so on.

Great changes are taking place in all fields of economy and science, and every teacher should widely acquaint his students with the next reconstructions and achievements in the field of science he teaches. It should be done in a way that is suitable for students and in accordance with the curriculum. The second feature of this requirement is that the pedagogue always cares about expanding the students' range of thought. Thus, teaching methods are activities aimed at fulfilling the educational tasks of pedagogues and students of theoretical and practical cognitive activities. The following specific requirements are imposed on it:

1. The method of studying the educational material recommended by the teacher should lead to the formation of students' dialectical views, positive characteristics and behavior. From the point of view of this requirement, the method should be educational.

2. The scientific basis of the teaching method should be clear and precise. Only then the teacher can see what problems can be posed and solved by this method, and what problems cannot be solved.

3. The systematicity of training determines its effectiveness.

4. Comprehensibility of the teaching method: the teaching method must be accepted and used by the student, and the method of studying the educational material must be in accordance with the possibilities of acquiring knowledge.

5. The need for awareness and activity of teaching is a very serious requirement.

6. Thoroughness and validity of knowledge is also crucial.

7. It is not possible to pass a lesson without achieving the compatibility of theoretical and practical events in the teaching method.

Changes and updates in the education system, along with giving students new knowledge, skills and qualifications, instill in our youth the patriotic ideas of change in relation to society, the state, nature, and other people. he also intends to instill it in his heart. A set of interrelated requirements represents a generalized model of a pedagogue and, based on it, the following basic requirements: the ability to teach, the ability to educate. Personal qualities that provide the human factor in the educational process are the ability to objectively assess and control the knowledge of learners. Therefore, a teacher pedagogue should have the following qualities in

order to fulfill the complex, responsible and urgent tasks set before him and to form new views on the educational process:

- able to deeply understand the essence of modern, scientific and cultural development;
- update the system of knowledge about the world and man from a deep and wide perspective;
- application of educational information technologies and teaching tools in education;
- to have an understanding of the Internet network and be able to use it to increase their knowledge;
- to know the ways of analyzing the effectiveness of pedagogical work and to be able to evaluate it;
- to develop ideas about family education and upbringing problems;
- to understand the essence of universal and national culture and economic reforms;
- to know how to effectively use pedagogical technologies in the course of the lesson;
- create conditions for students to think and exchange ideas with each other and create a friendly environment;
- knowing how to use technical tools and educational tools, such as educating children through their own research, creativity, initiative, and hard work, in order to make them become well-rounded people.

Any method is intended to achieve a goal, and therefore it requires setting a goal, a method of activity to achieve it, and knowing the tools that will help in the implementation of this activity. Any activity requires knowledge of its object. Finally, the method must lead to the goal, otherwise it must be recognized as unfit for its intended purpose.

Teaching methods can be divided into:

- methods that create content and activate special operations of thinking, memory, attention and imagination;
- methods that create problematic and searching situations in the activity of thoughts;
- methods that activate students' experiences and emotions related to mastering the learning material;
- methods of control and self-control of students;
- methods of managing students' spiritual and personal interactions during the teaching process.

CONCLUSION

Thus, any method requires the purpose of its application, the activities for the implementation of this goal, and the means of performance of the activity. These tools can be objective or intellectual knowledge about the object of activity, necessarily achieving the set goal. All of these are desirable for any method, but not sufficient for teaching methods.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE: (REFERENCES)

1. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
2. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.

3. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
4. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O 'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
5. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
6. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
7. Muradov, O. (2024, January). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. In *Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 46-55)*.
8. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *Models and methods in modern science*, 3(1), 84-93.
9. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 3(1), 54-63.
10. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 3(2), 16-27.
11. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 91–94).
12. Муродов, О. (2024). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПОМЕЩЕНИЯХ. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3,
13. Murodov, O. (2024). TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 3, сс. 155–160).
14. Murodov, O. (2024). INNOVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA INFORMATIKA VA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI FANINI O'QITISH JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 4, сс. 77–81).
15. Murodov, O. (2024). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 83–92).
16. Murodov Oybek Turakulovich. (2024). Development of an automated system for controlling temperature and humidity in production rooms. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 403–409.
17. Махмудова Нигора Хикматовна. (2024). Преподавание профильных предметов в начальной школе . *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 436–444.
18. Isomova, FATQ (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES IN PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 947-949.

19. G'aniyevna, P. R. F. (2022, June). MAKTABGA TAYYORLOV GURUHLARI UCHUN SAVODXONLIKKA O'RGATISH MASHG'ULOTLARIDA, A'HARF-TOVUSHINI O'RGATISH METODIKASI. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 38-41).

20. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). Tarbiya turlari va ularning shaxs kamolotiga ta'siri. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 429-435.

21. Tajiddinovna, I. F. (2024). Types of education and their impact on personality development. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 469-475.

22. Исомова, Ф. Т. (2024). Виды образования и их влияние на развитие личности. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 461-468.

23. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA "ILK QADAM" DASTURI. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 603-608.

24. Tajiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). FIRST STEP PROGRAM IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 609-614.

25. Tajiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). THE ISSUE OF EDUCATION IN PRIMARY EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 615-620.

26. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM JARAYONIDA BOLALARNING IJTIMOY MOSLASHUVI. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 590-595.

27. Рузиева, М. (2023). ТАРЖИМА ПЛАТФОРМАСИ-МУТАРЖИМ ЛИСОНИЙ ТАФАККУРИНИНГ КЎЗГУСИ. *Наука и технология в современном мире*, 2(20), 37-39.

28. Рузиева, М. Я., & Эргашева, Т. Ш. (2022). МЕТОДЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ УЧЕБНЫХ СЛОВАРЕЙ НА УРОКАХ РОДНОГО ЯЗЫКА И ЧТЕНИЯ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ. *Вестник науки и образования*, (2-2 (122)), 29-32.

29. Narziyeva, S. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL VIEWS ON THE CHOICE OF PROFESSION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 333-336.

30. Rustamovna, N. S. (2023). UNDERSTANDING EMPATHY: AN ESSENTIAL COMPONENT OF HUMAN CONNECTION. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 378-382.

31. Rustamovna, N. S. (2023). DEVELOPING EMPATHY IN STUDENTS. *Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(3), 127-131. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT O'QUV JARAYONI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING MUHIM OMILI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(8), 131-139.

32. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT O'QUV JARAYONI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING MUHIM OMILI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(8), 131-139.

33. Khalilova, S. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF GLOBALIZATION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 28, 6-11.

34. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Bo 'lajak o'qituvchi pedagogik muloqot usullarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasining zamonaviy modellari va ularni qo'llash metodlari. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(9), 223-234.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

35. XALILOVA, S. (2021). JAHON PEDAGOGIKASIDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT VA MILLIY PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT USLUBLARIGA TRANSFORMATSIYASI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 1(1).
36. Ravshanovna, K. S. (2023). Factors Affecting the Formation of a Positive Attitude to the Learning Activity in Students. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 116-122.
37. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Globallashuv sharoitida o'quvchilar aqliy-ruhiy qiyofasini shakllantirishda muloqot uslublarining ahamiyati. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 100-106.
38. Ravshnovna, K. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE CULTURE OF COMMUNICATION IN MODERN EDUCATION AND EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 356-361.
39. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2022). BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILAR VA O'QUVCHILAR O'RTASIDAGI MULOQOT JARAYONI VA UNGA QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR. *Лучший инноватор в области науки*, 1(1), 814-819.
40. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida pedagogik muloqot usullarining o'zlashtirish jarayoniga ta'siri va ahamiyati. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(10), 803-816.
41. Xalilova Shaxlo Ravshanovna. (2024). The teacher's views on the technologies for the development of pedagogical communication methods. *МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА*, 2(2), 368–376.
42. Халилова, Ш. Р. (2024). Технологии разработки методов педагогического общения в образовательном процессе сделанный увеличивать технологии. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 261-268.
43. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2024). PEDAGOGLAR TOMONIDAN DARSDA VA DARSDAN TASHQARI MUHITDA QO'LLANADIGAN PEDAGOGIK MULOQOTNING USLUBLARI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 126-134.
44. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT AS A SOCIAL-BIOLOGICAL PHENOMENON, AS AN OBJECT AND SUBJECT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
45. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Teachers by before school education organization in pupils passable training in the process to the children applied pedagogical communication styles classification. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 237-243.
46. O'ktam qizi Buxoro, S. M. (2022). BOLANING NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI O'YINLAR. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 1(1), 484-486.
47. Oktam's, S. M. (2023). Methods and Tools of Speech Development of Small Group Children in Preschool Education Organization. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 104-108.
48. O'ktam qizi Shukurova, M. (2023). Speech grow up in training using interactive methods. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 357-360.
49. O'ktam qizi Shukurova, M. (2023). The importance of genres of folklore in the education of preschool children. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 96-99.

50. Shukurova, M. (2023). METHODS AND METHODS OF INCREASING CHILDREN'S SPEECH IN A PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 477–480.
51. Madina O'ktamovna Shukurova. (2024). " Growing children's speech in the process of introducing them to the environment and nature ". *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 130–135.
52. Shukurova, M. (2024). OILADA FARZAND TARBIYASIDA OTANING ROLI. ZAMONAVIY TARAQQIYOTDA ILM-FAN VA MADANIYATNING O 'RNI, 3(2), 162-167.
53. O'ktamovna, S. M. (2024). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМДА ТАБИАТ BURCHAGINI TAYYORLASH. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 661-667.
54. O'ktamovna, S. M. (2024). EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY GRADES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 654-660.
55. O'ktamovna, S. M. (2024). PREPARATION OF THE NATURE CORNER IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 675-681.
56. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2023). НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОЗДАНИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СЛУЖБЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *ЛКИИСИ РАН, МАПН, 2023–267 с.*, 13.
57. Баратов, Ш. Р., & Сабирова, Д. А. (2016). Социальный интеллект как необходимое качество педагога. *История российской психологии в лицах: Дайджест-ISSN 2415-7953 (РИНЦ)*, (6).
58. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2018). Психологик хизмат: Магистрлар учун дарслик. *Т.: "Наврўз" нашириёти*, 344.
59. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2015). A role of social intellekt and social competence in professional development of a teacher in the intense training system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 3(4), 43-48.
60. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2012). Социальный Интеллект: Структура и Функции. *Психология XXI столетия*, 2, 153-158.
61. Баротов, Ш. Р. (1995). Ўқувчи шахсини ўрганиш усуллари. *Т.: Ўқитувчи*, 57.
62. Баратов, Ш. Р. (2021). Из опыта внедрения концепции психологической службы в Узбекистане. "XXI АСР ПСИХОЛОГИЯСИ" МАВЗУСИДАГИ ХАЛҚАРО ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ АНЖУМАНИ МАҚОЛАЛАР ТЎПЛАМИ, 5.
63. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2017). Психологическая служба образования: от теории к практике.(Учебно-методическое пособие). *Бухара: Дурдона*.